

SUMMARY.

1. The surface tension and density of the hydrochlorides and coloured carbinol-bases of rosaniline, crystal violet and malachite green have been determined in solution and the parachor calculated.

2. The parachor values were found to agree with the quinonoid structure suggested by Nietzki.

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A Yellow Colouring Matter from the Wood of *Adina Cordifolia*, Hook.

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Adina cordifolia (Hook) which is known as "Keli-Kadam" in Bengal and "Naldu" in Hindusthani, is a large deciduous tree which is found to be fairly well distributed throughout the whole of northern India as well as Bengal, Assam and Burma. In most of the forests it grows profusely and very often it is planted as a road-side or avenue tree. The wood is very even-grained, moderately hard, lemon-yellow in colour when freshly cut but turning yellowish grey on exposure and weighs 45 pounds per cubic foot. It is suitable for furniture making and in northern India combs are made out of this wood as well as toys and drums. The colouring matter of this wood is very easily removed by extraction with boiling water or organic solvents and as no work seems to have been done before on this subject, the present investigation was undertaken with a view to the isolation of the colouring matter in a pure state and elucidation of its constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A big log of the authentic specimen of the wood was procured from Messrs. Bhupat Lal & Sons, Wood Merchants, Allahabad, and was converted into shavings. For exhaustive extraction with

different solvents, the coarsely powdered shavings were taken in 20 g. lots in a Soxhlet's extractor, and after filtration, the solvent was evaporated in each case and the residue brought to a constant weight by heating in a steam-oven. The following results were obtained.

Aqueous extract.—The extract was bright yellow at first, but during the course of heating in the steam-oven, it gradually became brown. Microscopic examination revealed the presence of colourless crystals of calcium oxalate and the substance gave strong reactions of tannins and sugars, yield 5.18%. No essential or fixed oil could be detected.

Chloroform extract.—The substance was a pale yellow wax, yield 0.02%.

Petroleum ether extract.—This was practically identical with the chloroform extract, yield 0.03%.

Acetone extract.—It was a light yellow semi-solid substance with colourless crystals of calcium oxalate disseminated throughout the entire mass, yield 3.67%. In general properties it is quite similar to the alcoholic extract.

Alcoholic extract.—It was an orange-yellow semi-solid mass with a characteristic smell of the wood and a slight astringent taste, yield 6.88%. It gives a green colouration with neutral alcoholic ferric chloride, a pale yellow precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate and an intense yellow colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. Caustic alkalis yield a yellowish brown colouration which darkens on exposure to the air. The substance reduces Fehling's solution and ammoniacal silver nitrate and gives negative tests with alkaloid reagents. Calcium oxalate is present in the substance in fairly large quantities and can be easily isolated.

Isolation of Adinin.

1 Kg. of small shavings of the wood was repeatedly extracted with 95% alcohol in a 5 litre extraction flask until the extract was practically colourless. The combined orange-yellow extracts were distilled at the ordinary pressure until practically the whole of solvent had distilled over and the residue began to froth vigorously. It was then allowed to stand for a week at the end of which a large amount of crystalline matter separated out in the form of yellow nodules. This was filtered off, washed with small quantities of alcohol and dried in the steam-oven. The substance was then freed from waxy impurities by extraction with hot benzene and the

purified material thus obtained was recrystallised several times from hot alcohol. The pure substance crystallises from alcohol in long,

Adinin from acetic acid ($\times 250$)

Adinin from alcohol ($\times 250$)

fine, glistening needles with a golden yellow colour and from glacial acetic acid in small bright yellow prisms the microphotographs of which are shown above. The substance on heating darkens in colour at 195° - 96° becoming orange-red, shrinks at 200° and above that temperature gradually darkens and decomposes without melting. The substance is practically insoluble in cold and only slightly soluble in boiling water and undergoes decomposition on protracted boiling. It is insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, ether, petroleum ether and carbon disulphide. It is slightly soluble in cold and moderately soluble in hot alcohol, acetone and glacial acetic acid. It dissolves readily in solutions of alkali hydroxides but less readily in alkali carbonates and bicarbonates, forming light yellow solutions, from which the colouring matter is reprecipitated unchanged on acidification. The substance although neutral in reaction, dissolves in concentrated mineral acids like hydrochloric, hydrobromic, hydroiodic, nitric and sulphuric acids, forming bright yellow solutions, the colours of which are much more intense than that of the corresponding concentration of the colouring matter in alcoholic solution. Alcoholic solution of the substance gives no precipitate or colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, lead acetate, calcium chloride or silver nitrate. The substance does not reduce Fehling's solution either before or after boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid, thereby showing its non-glucosidal nature. The substance in alcoholic hydrochloric acid on treatment with metallic

magnesium becomes reduced to a colourless substance thereby showing that it is not a colouring matter belonging to the flavone groups which by this treatment would have been reduced to a red or violet coloured flavylum salt. The alcoholic solution of the substance shows a bright green fluorescence which becomes more intense in ultraviolet light, in which also the substance dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid shows a violet fluorescence and its solution in phenol a greenish blue fluorescence. These apparently point to the presence of an anthraquinone, a xanthone or an isoflavone nucleus in the molecule. The absence of an anthraquinone nucleus was proved by the fact that on treatment with zinc dust and ammonia it did not give any red, blue or violet colouration, but became altogether colourless.

In alcoholic solution it is optically inactive. From 10 kg. of the shavings 9.1 g. of the pure substance were isolated (yield 0.09%). [Found (specimen dried at 120°): C, 60.58, 60.28, 60.50, 60.32; H, 4.63, 4.83, 4.51, 4.64. M. W. (cryoscopically in phenol), 299, 293, 290. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 60.4; H, 4.4 per cent. M.W., 318]. [Found (specimen dried in vacuum desiccator for 10 days): C, 56.55, 56.83; H, 4.83, 4.85. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7, H_2O$, requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent]. The air-dried substance lost 16.2, 15.9, 16.3% of H_2O at 120° and 9.8, 9.6% of H_2O in the vacuum desiccator in the course of 10 days. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7, 3H_2O$ requires for loss of $2H_2O$, 9.67% and for loss of $3H_2O$, 14.7%.

It is clear from the analytical data that the substance crystallises from 95% alcohol with three molecules of water of crystallisation of which it loses two in the vacuum desiccator and all the three at 120°. No compound of this formula and possessing properties identical with it has been recorded in chemical literature. It is therefore, proposed to designate this new compound "adinin" with reference to its properties as a colouring matter and the generic name of the plant from which it has been isolated.

Demethylation of adinin.—A carefully weighed amount of adinin dried at 120° was heated with freshly distilled hydroiodic acid (*d*, 1.72) in accordance with the method of Zeisel for the estimation of methoxy groups. The precipitated silver iodide was filtered off, washed with dilute nitric acid, dried at 120° and weighed. (Found: OMe, 10.1, 9.9. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6 \cdot OMe$ requires OMe, 9.74 per cent).

norAdinin.—The collective product from the action of hydroiodic acid, which was evidently present in the form of an oxonium salt, was

poured into sodium hydrogen sulphite solution, and the yellow precipitate collected. It crystallises from boiling glacial acetic acid in the form of yellow needles which shrink at 213-14° and decomposes above 232° without melting. It is practically insoluble in cold or hot water, alcohol, acetone, benzene, ether, chloroform and petroleum ether and is fairly soluble in hot acetic acid. Alcoholic ferric chloride gives a dirty greenish grey colour with the alcoholic solution of the substance and alcoholic lead acetate throws down a pale yellow precipitate. *nor*Adinin has not yet been obtained in sufficient quantity for combustion.

Adinin hydrobromide.—Adinin (0.5 g.) dried at 120° was treated with the minimum quantity of concentrated hydrobromic acid (d 1.78), sufficient to dissolve it. The substance dissolved immediately forming an intense yellow solution and the clock-glass containing it was kept in a vacuum desiccator containing granulated solid caustic potash for a number of days. The product when completely dry was washed with dry ether and finally dried in the vacuum desiccator. The hydrobromide was thus obtained in the form of bright orange-yellow needles which shrink at 159-60° and decompose above 200° without melting. (Found: Br, 22.6. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7$, HBr requires Br, 20.05 per cent).

Ammonium salt of adinin was obtained by dissolving 0.5 g. of adinin in the smallest quantity of pure concentrated ammonia and allowing the solution to evaporate at the ordinary temperature in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid for several days. The salt was obtained as orange-yellow crusts which shrink at 104°.5°, completely melt at 130°, solidify and again melt at 202°.3° with frothing. On exposure to air it gradually loses ammonium and becomes converted into a mixture of adinin and the ammonia salt of varying composition. The substance could not be obtained in a state of sufficient purity for analysis.

Absorption spectra of adinin.—An alcoholic solution of adinin (1%) on spectrographic examination was found to have a well-defined absorption band between wave-length 4250-4650Å, with the head of the band or absorption maxima at 4590Å.

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